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Wind turbine power performance characterization through aeroelastic simulations and virtual nacelle lidar measurements

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Abstract. The power performance of a wind turbine depends on several characteristics of the inflow, such as wind speed, turbulence and wind shear. Additionally, wind turbine control strategies affect the power performance of the wind turbines; under certain conditions one might want to, e.g., intentionally misalign the turbine with respect to the main wind direction. Here, we evaluate whether the accuracy in power performance evaluation can be improved by using multi-dimensional power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions, which define the power output as function of wind speed, turbulence and yaw misalignment. The analysis is conducted on a dataset of virtual power performance measurements, which is generated through aeroelastic simulations combined with a simulator of nacelle lidar measurements. Results show that the multi-dimensional power curves can provide higher accuracy than those derived using the IEC standard for power curve measurements; the error in power prediction is nearly halved compared to that using the IEC standard power curve method. Additionally, we show that nacelle lidar measurements increase the accuracy of the multi-dimensional power curves when compared to using mast-based anemometer measurements.

1. Introduction

The first version of the IEC standard for power performance measurements described the power output of a wind turbine as function of only two flow characteristics: the air density and the mean wind speed at hub height [1]. However, studies have shown that wind turbine power performance is affected by other flow characteristics, such as atmospheric turbulence and wind shear [2; 3]. Because of the non-linearity of the power curve, the mean¹ power output depends on both the mean and the variance of the wind speed. Where the power curve is concave, e.g. for wind speeds slightly higher than the cut-in value, the mean power output increases with the wind speed variance. On the contrary, where the power curve is convex, e.g. for wind speeds slightly lower than the rated-value, the mean power output decreases with the wind speed variance. This expected behavior was confirmed by several studies through both simulations and measurements [2; 4; 5]. Additionally, neglecting the wind speed variation with height might result in a poor estimation of the kinetic energy flux through the rotor [3]. Therefore, in the most recent version of the IEC standard [6] for power performance measurements, both wind shear and atmospheric turbulence are considered. These additional flow characteristics increase the accuracy of the

¹ mean here refer to the average within a 10-min period

power performance assessment, resulting in more reliable power curves and less uncertainty in energy yield assessment (EYA).

Nevertheless, in order to guarantee an accurate EYA, it is crucial to account for flow inhomogeneities from the atmosphere-wind turbine interaction and evaluate their effect on the power performance. Previous studies used both parametric and non-parametric models to evaluate wind turbine power performance under different environmental conditions [7–9]. Recently, wake steering, which is a control strategy, introduced the need to evaluate the power performance of a wind turbine under yawed conditions, i.e. when the mean wind direction and the turbine rotor axis are misaligned [10]. Previous studies showed how to correct standard power curves for yaw misalignment [10; 11] in order to evaluate the effects of wake steering in EYA.

In this work, we evaluate whether the accuracy in power performance evaluation can be improved by using multi-variable power curves, which define the power output as function of wind speed, turbulence and yaw misalignment. The analysis is conducted on a dataset of power performance simulations. Specifically, numerical wind fields are generated with the turbulence spectral model of Mann [12], and the in-house aeroelastic code HAWC2 [13] is used to perform time-domain aeroelastic simulations. Additionally, we simulate measurements from a nacelle-mounted lidar to evaluate whether the accuracy of the new multi-variable power curve changes when using nacelle-mounted lidars instead of traditional mast-based anemometry.

This paper is organized as follows. The methodology is outlined in section 2, which describes the numerical wind fields in section 2.1, the lidar simulator in section 2.2 and the multi-dimensional power curves in section 2.3. Section 3 shows and discusses the accuracy of the multi-dimensional power curves. Conclusions are given in section 5.

2. Methodology

2.1. Generation of the dataset

The turbulence model by Mann is used to generate three-dimensional velocity fields $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$, with $\mathbf{u} = (u, v, w)$ being the along-wind, transverse, and vertical velocity components and $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ the spatial field. The wind fields are characterized by homogeneous frozen turbulence, with the wind speed fluctuations $\mathbf{u}' = (u', v', w')$ advected along the horizontal axis x . Therefore, assuming homogeneity and no vertical wind speed, the mean wind speed varies with height according to the chosen shear profile: $\mathbf{U} = (U(z), 0, 0)$. In case of no vertical shear, the mean wind speed is uniform in the (y, z) plane.

The turbulence fields are used as input to the HAWC2 aeroelastic simulations [13], which are performed with the Vestas V52 wind turbine, with a rotor diameter (D) of 52 m and a rated power of 900 kW. According to the IEC standard [6], power performance measurements are based on 10-min means of both wind speed and power output. Therefore, in order to get a 10-min mean power output from each aeroelastic simulation, all the wind fields have dimensions of $(UT, 128 \text{ m}, 128 \text{ m})$. We choose $T = 700 \text{ s}$; the additional 100 s are needed to avoid the initial transient phase of the aeroelastic simulation, while the length of 128 m is used in both the vertical and lateral directions to ensure enough distance between the rotor and the edge of the turbulence field, avoiding possible bias due to the field periodicity [14].

We generate two different datasets, hereafter referred to as the synthetic and realistic dataset. The synthetic dataset is shaped in order to guarantee a data distribution that is convenient for the evaluation of the multi-dimensional power curves. On the other hand, the realistic dataset aims to replicate the data distribution that would be collected from a real wind turbine operating under optimal conditions. Both datasets present turbulence fields generated with the Mann-model length scale of $L = 29.4 \text{ m}$ and anisotropy of $\Gamma = 3.9$, while the other Mann-model parameter $\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$ is varied to match the desired turbulence level. The synthetic dataset consists of 720 wind fields characterized by a uniform distribution of U between 6.5 and 12 m/s. Half

Table 1. Flow characteristics of the numerical wind fields in the different datasets. $[a, b]$ indicates a uniform or nearly uniform distribution between a and b . $N(\mu, \sigma)$ indicates a Gaussian distribution with μ and σ as mean and standard deviation, respectively. A single value indicates a constant over the whole dataset

Dataset	U [m/s]	L [m]	Γ	$\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$ [$\text{m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$]	γ [$^\circ$]	α	N
Synthetic (1 st half)	[6.5, 12]	29.4	3.9	[0.005, 0.165]	0	0	360
Synthetic (2 nd half)	[6.5, 12]	29.4	3.9	0.03	[-40,+40]	0	360
Realistic	[6, 14]	29.4	3.9	$N(0.06, 0.02)$	$N(0, 3)$	$N(0.15, 0.1)$	150

of this dataset (360 wind fields) presents a uniform turbulence distribution obtained by varying the $\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$ parameter between 0.005 and 0.165 $\text{m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$ and no yaw misalignment ($\gamma = 0^\circ$). In the other half, turbulence is kept constant ($\alpha\epsilon = 0.03 \text{ m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$) and γ is varied between $\pm 40^\circ$. Additionally, all wind fields of the synthetic dataset have a uniform mean wind speed (no vertical shear). The realistic dataset consists of 150 wind fields characterized by sheared inflows and Gaussian distributions (μ representing the mean and σ the standard deviation) for $\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$, γ and the shear exponent α ($\mu_{\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}} = 0.06 \text{ m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$, $\sigma_{\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}} = 0.02 \text{ m}^{4/3}/\text{s}$; $\mu_\gamma = 0^\circ$, $\sigma_\gamma = 3^\circ$; $\mu_\alpha = 0.15$, $\sigma_\alpha = 0.1$). The mean wind speed is varied between 6 and 14 m/s according to the wind speed distribution retrieved from wind-speed measurements on the west coast of Denmark [15].

In order to simulate the wind speed measurements close to a real power performance test, 10-min mean wind speeds are retrieved from the numerical wind fields from both virtual sonic anemometer (hereafter referred to as sonics) and nacelle-mounted lidar measurements. Specifically, we place one sonic anemometer at hub height and six more sonic anemometers along the vertical coordinate at distances of $\pm 6, \pm 14$ and ± 22 m from hub height. In this way, we obtain 10-min mean values of both power output and wind speed at seven different levels, similarly to a real power performance test where the wind speed is measured in front of an operating wind turbine.

2.2. Lidar simulations and wind-speed reconstruction

The lidar simulator scans the same velocity fields used as input to the aeroelastic simulations without considering the impact of the wind turbine, i.e., the induction zone in front of the rotor is not modelled. We simulate measurements from the DTU SpinnerLidar [16], which is a continuous-wave Doppler wind lidar that scans over the rose pattern shown in figure 1-a. Similar to [16], we assume that at the 400 locations of the rose pattern, shown as filled circles in figure 1, we obtain 400 averaged Doppler radial velocity spectra for each full scan. The system is set to generate a rose pattern every 2 s, so we get 300 Doppler spectra at each of the 400 scanning locations within a 10-min period. The SpinnerLidar is characterized by a laser wavelength of 1.565 μm and a lens aperture radius of 28 mm, which result in the weighting function φ shown in figure 1-b when the SpinnerLidar is focused at 1D in front of the rotor. In order to provide a good estimation of the probe-volume effect without getting out of the turbulence-box boundaries, we model the probe volume over a distance of 20 times the Rayleigh length Z_r , which is a lidar characteristic length defined by the laser wavelength, the lens radius and the focus distance. The portion of weighting function within $\pm 10 Z_r$ around the focus point is highlighted in red in figure 1-b.

Figure 1. (a) Scanning configuration of the SpinnerLidar (*blue*) focused at 1D in front of the rotor (*red*). (b) Weighting function of the SpinnerLidar focused at 1D.

The simulated Doppler radial velocity spectrum is obtained as

$$S(v_r, t) = \int_{-10Z_r}^{10Z_r} \varphi(s) \cdot \delta(v_r - \mathbf{u}(s) \cdot \mathbf{n}) ds, \quad (1)$$

where s is the distance from the focus point along the lidar beam direction, v_r is the velocity component along the beam (radial velocity), \mathbf{n} is the unit vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)$ along the beam direction and δ is the Dirac delta function. Equation 1 can be viewed as a weighted histogram distribution of v_r , which returns the weighted frequency of the considered value within the probe volume. We choose a discretization of 0.1 m/s for the histogram distribution in order to match the typical velocity resolution of a real lidar system. The measured radial velocity is then retrieved as the first statistical moment of the Doppler spectrum:

$$v_r(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} v_r \cdot S(v_r, t) dv_r. \quad (2)$$

The radial velocity variance $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ is estimated as the second central moment of the ensemble averaged Doppler spectrum $\mathbf{S}(v_r) = \langle S(v_r, t) \rangle$ in order to avoid turbulence filtering caused by the probe-volume effect [17]:

$$\sigma_{v_r}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{S}(v_r) (v_r - \bar{v}_r)^2 dv_r, \quad (3)$$

where \bar{v}_r is the first moment of $\mathbf{S}(v_r)$. The virtual measurements of v_r and $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ are then used to reconstruct both the mean and variance of the wind speed over the 10-min interval.

In order to estimate the 10-min mean wind speed $\mathbf{U} = (U, V, W)$, the lidar beams are clustered in bins according to their height with a discretization of $\Delta z = 1$ m, so that the wind speed can be assumed as homogeneous within each bin despite of the wind shear. Consequently, the mean wind speed at each height $U(z)$ is retrieved by applying a least-square fit to all the beams within the same bin:

$$\Delta^2 = \int (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{U} - \langle v_r \rangle)^2 d\mu, \quad (4)$$

where $\langle v_r \rangle$ is the ensemble average of the 300 radial velocities measured at each of the positions in the rose pattern during the 10-min period. Since the wind fields are homogeneous with regards

to turbulence, the Reynolds stress tensor \mathbf{R} is assumed as uniform over the whole scanned area. Therefore, the Reynolds stresses $R_{ij} = \langle u'_i u'_j \rangle$ are retrieved by applying a least-square fit to all the beams:

$$\Delta^2 = \int (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{R} \mathbf{n} - \sigma_{v_r}^2)^2 d\mu. \quad (5)$$

More details about the mean and turbulence reconstruction techniques can be found in [18].

2.3. Evaluation of the multi-dimensional power curves

After carrying out the HAWC2 simulations and scanning the wind fields with the virtual lidar, we get two datasets with 720 (synthetic dataset) and 150 (realistic dataset) observations of 6 attributes: U from both SpinnerLidar and sonics, the first Reynolds stress component $\langle u'u' \rangle = \sigma_u^2$ from both SpinnerLidar and sonics, $\cos(\gamma)$ and the 10-min mean power output P . The mean wind speed U is evaluated as the wind speed at hub height in the synthetic dataset, while in the realistic dataset, U is the rotor equivalent wind speed defined as in [3]. It should be noted that in cases of yaw misalignment $\gamma \neq 0^\circ$, U measured by the SpinnerLidar represents the wind-speed component perpendicular to the rotor instead of the horizontal wind speed, as the nacelle-mounted lidar yaws with the turbine.

The two datasets are used to define three different multi-variable power curves: $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2)$, $P = P(U, \gamma)$ and $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$, where U and σ_u^2 are measured from the SpinnerLidar or the sonics. The multi-variable power curves are modelled as multivariate polynomial regressions, whose input attributes consist of a polynomial combination of the original attributes with degree less than or equal to the specified degree β . For example, for the bivariate power curve $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ with $\beta = 2$, we get the following polynomial expression: $y = c_1 + c_2 x_1 + c_3 x_2 + c_4 x_1^2 + c_5 x_2^2 + c_6 x_1 x_2$, where $y = P$, $x_1 = U$, $x_2 = \sigma_u^2$ and c_1, \dots, c_6 are the regression coefficients. When accounting for the yaw misalignment γ , the input attributes are $X = [U, \cos(\gamma)]$ and $X = [U, \sigma_u^2, \cos(\gamma)]$ for the bivariate and trivariate cases, respectively. For each multi-variable power curve, we evaluate nine values of β from the first to the ninth order.

Each regression model is tested through a K-fold cross-validation with $K = 10$: the dataset is randomly split into 10 sub-datasets (folds) presenting the same number of observations, and each fold is used as testing dataset, while the training dataset consists of the other nine folds. This results in training and testing the model ten times obtaining ten different test errors E_j , which are computed as the root mean square deviation between the estimated power output P^{est} and the reference value given by the aeroelastic simulations P , i.e., $E_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_i (P_i^{est} - P_i)^2}$, where N is the number of observations in the testing fold. Models are evaluated by looking at the generalization error $\lambda = \frac{1}{10} \sum_j E_j$. This procedure ensures that the final error λ does not depend on how the dataset is split into training and testing sets, since the model is tested over all the observations.

3. Results

The accuracy of the multi-dimensional power curves is compared to that of the IEC standard power curve, which is defined according to the latest IEC standard [6]. In case the wind field is characterized by shear, we correct for the wind shear by using the rotor equivalent wind speed, while we do not apply any turbulence normalization. This is in line with the standard, as both wind-shear and turbulence corrections are recommended but not mandatory procedures [6].

When the synthetic dataset is used to define the power curves, all the multi-dimensional power curves are more accurate than the IEC standard power curve, as shown in figure 2-a. Both $P(U, \gamma)$ and $P(U, \gamma, \sigma_u^2)$ outperform the IEC standard due to the strong yaw misalignment that cannot be characterized by the standard power curve. Additionally, also the bivariate power curve $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ provides higher accuracy than that using the IEC standard, showing the benefits of including turbulence to analyze the power output. For $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$, the SpinnerLidar is

much more accurate than the sonic, as the SpinnerLidar measures the wind-speed component perpendicular to the rotor despite the yaw misalignment. Between the two bivariate power curves, $P(U, \gamma)$ is the most accurate due to the cases of very large yaw misalignment (up to 40°), which make the correlation between P and γ stronger than that between P and σ_u^2 . However, the highest accuracy is given by considering both γ and σ_u^2 ; compared to the IEC standard, the error is reduced by 79% and 80% for the sonic and the SpinnerLidar, respectively.

Figure 2 also shows how the generalization error changes with the degree of the polynomial regressions. As seen in the figure, the optimal value of β varies for the different power curves. For the three-dimensional power curves, λ strongly decreases up to $\beta = 3$, remains nearly constant for $3 \leq \beta \leq 5$ and quickly increases for $\beta \geq 6$, with the same trend for both SpinnerLidar and sonic. The bivariate regressions present a larger interval of nearly optimal values for β , with values of λ close to the minimum within $3 \leq \beta \leq 7$ and $3 \leq \beta \leq 9$ when considering σ_u^2 and γ , respectively.

Figure 2. (a) Generalization error of power curves defined with the synthetic dataset when using the optimal β . (b) Variation of λ with the order of the polynomial regressions $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ (squares), $P(U, \gamma)$ (triangles) and $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ (circles) based on sonic (blue) and SpinnerLidar (orange); optimal values are highlighted in red.

Figure 3 shows scatter plots of the power estimated by both the SpinnerLidar-based and the IEC power curves against the reference power given by the aeroelastic simulations for the synthetic dataset. Each scatter plot presents 720 points for both power curves since all the power values in the dataset are used for testing due to the cross validation. As shown in the figure, the multi-dimensional power curves provide a very good correlation between the estimated and reference power values without significant outliers, especially in the three-dimensional case.

When the realistic dataset is used to define the power curves, as shown in figure 4, only the bivariate regression $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ is more accurate than that of the IEC standard. Similar to the results using the synthetic dataset, the SpinnerLidar provides higher accuracy than the sonic as the yaw misalignment is inherently accounted for. However, when γ is an input attribute to the regression, both the bivariate and trivariate regressions fail to outperform the IEC standard power curve for both sonic and SpinnerLidar measurements. This is due to the distribution of γ in the realistic dataset, which does not allow a proper training of the models.

When using the realistic dataset for training and testing, nearly all the multivariate

Figure 3. Scatter plots of the power estimated by both SpinnerLidar-based regressions and IEC standard power curve against the reference power for the synthetic dataset

Figure 4. (a) Generalization error of power curves defined with the realistic dataset when using the optimal β . (b) Variation of λ with the order of the polynomial regressions $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ (squares), $P(U, \gamma)$ (triangles) and $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ (circles) based on sonic (blue) and SpinnerLidar (orange); optimal values are highlighted in red.

regressions present the lowest error for $\beta = 3$ or $\beta = 4$, except for the SpinnerLidar-based $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$, which presents $\beta = 5$ as the optimal case. Additionally, for the three-dimensional case $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$, λ quickly increases for $\beta > 3$ for both sonic- and SpinnerLidar-based power curves. Despite the higher mean error compared to the result of the IEC standard, figure 5 shows that the multi-dimensional power curves provide a reliable estimation of the power output, without resulting in large outliers.

Due to the differences in the results when analyzing the synthetic and realistic datasets, a third analysis is performed combining the two datasets. Specifically, all the multivariate polynomial regressions are trained on the synthetic dataset and tested on the realistic one. In this case, the models are evaluated based on the root mean square error instead of λ , since the models are only trained and tested once, without performing any cross-validation. As shown in figure 6, all the models including γ outperform the IEC standard power curve, with a clear

Figure 5. Scatter plots of the power estimated by both SpinnerLidar-based regressions and IEC standard power curve against the reference power for the realistic dataset

improvement compared to the case when the models are both trained and tested on the realistic dataset. This confirms that the realistic dataset is not suitable for training the models due to the low and non-uniformly distributed values of γ .

Furthermore, it should be noted that for the two-dimensional case $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$, only the SpinnerLidar outperforms the IEC standard, while the sonic provides an increase of the error. In this case, information about σ_u^2 does not benefit the power estimations; only when accounting for the yaw misalignment we observe the benefits. However, for both sonic and SpinnerLidar measurements, $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ outperforms $P(U, \gamma)$, showing that σ_u^2 adds valuable information to the model when γ is already known.

The three-dimensional power curve $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ provides the highest accuracy with an error of 7.2 kW and 6.4 kW for the sonic and the SpinnerLidar, respectively. When compared to the error of the IEC standard power curve (12.2 kW), this means a reduction of 41% and 48%. Differently from the case of figure 2, where the difference between sonics and SpinnerLidar is negligible, SpinnerLidar-based two-dimensional power curves perform better than those based on sonics. This is probably due to a better characterization of the wind shear and the kinetic energy flux throughout the rotor.

As shown in figure 6, the error of the three-dimensional power curve reaches the minimum for $\beta = 4$ and steeply increases for $\beta > 4$, further confirming the results in figure 2. Only when training the model with the realistic dataset, the trivariate regression presents $\beta = 3$ as the optimal case. However, that case can be neglected since the realistic dataset is not suitable to train the trivariate regression. In the two-dimensional cases $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ and $P(U, \gamma)$, the error is nearly constant for a large number of degrees, similarly to the case of figure 2. Although it is not shown here, scatter plots for the case of figure 6 look similarly to those of figures 3 and 5, with very good correlation and without any outliers.

Figure 7 shows how the power output varies with σ_u^2 and γ according to the trivariate power curve $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ trained over the whole synthetic dataset and whose accuracy is shown in figure 6. In order to show the effect of the two variables σ_u^2 and γ , we use two different data distributions: in figures 7-(a,c), we have constant $\gamma = 0^\circ$ and the same variation of U and σ_u^2 as in the synthetic dataset; in figures 7-(b,d), we have constant $\sigma_u^2 = 0.5 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ and the same variation of U and γ as in the synthetic dataset. As it can be seen in figures 7-(a,c), higher turbulence increases the power output for wind speed values close to cut-in, while it decreases the power output closely to the rated value. The yaw misalignment γ decreases the power output irrespective of the wind speed, as confirmed by figure 7-b. The effect seems to be the opposite

when looking at figure 7-d, as U represents the wind-speed component orthogonal to the rotor when using SpinnerLidar measurements. Consequently, in case of same U and different γ , higher γ means higher free-stream velocity. This effect on the power curve should not be misunderstood as a positive correlation between γ and P .

Figure 6. (a) Error of power curves trained on the synthetic dataset and tested on the realistic dataset when using the optimal β . (b) Variation of the error with the order of the polynomial regressions $P(U, \sigma_u^2)$ (squares), $P(U, \gamma)$ (triangles) and $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ (circles) based on sonic (blue) and SpinnerLidar (orange); optimal values are highlighted in red.

4. Discussion

Wind turbine power performance is modelled through multivariate power curves in the form of polynomial regressions, which present three input attributes: the mean wind speed U , the atmospheric turbulence evaluated as the wind speed variance σ_u^2 and the yaw misalignment γ . We do not include the shear exponent α as an input to the regressions as we account for the wind shear through the rotor equivalent wind speed. This likely gives similar accuracy to adding a 4th term to the regression, without increasing the numerical complexity of the model. The evaluation of α as a 4th input to the multivariate power curves could be part of the further development of this work.

The multivariate power curves are tested on a dataset consisting of virtual flow measurements. Therefore, one could question to which extent this approach would be affected by the uncertainties related to real field measurements. We are confident that the virtual flow measurements are a reliable and accurate representation of what we would get from field measurements, as long as these were conducted under nearly homogeneous conditions. In case of inhomogeneous conditions, the wind speed reconstruction described in section 2.2 would be unreliable, so that a different approach is needed to accurately retrieve U and σ_u^2 from the SpinnerLidar measurements v_r and $\sigma_{v_r}^2$. However, even when the assumption of homogeneity is rather crude, we expect the multivariate power curves to perform well. The difference is that the multivariate power curve will relate the power output to the lidar-derived characteristics rather than to the “true” flow characteristics. Additionally, when testing the multi-dimensional power curves with measurements out in the field, their accuracy might be challenged by the uncertainty in the estimation of the yaw misalignment, which is known in our virtual setup. Therefore,

Figure 7. Power curves given by the trivariate regression $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ based on sonic (a, b) and SpinnerLidar (c, d) with $\gamma = 0^\circ$ (a, c) and $\sigma_u^2 = 0.5 \text{m}^2/\text{s}^2$ (b, d)

nacelle lidar measurements are needed to estimate the yaw misalignment more accurately than with, e.g., traditional nacelle-based wind vanes.

Testing the multivariate power curves under inhomogeneous conditions would be an interesting topic for future research. Additionally, it would be interesting to evaluate the necessary range of γ available in the training dataset in order to obtain accurate curves. Probably, in the synthetic dataset, we considered a larger γ interval ($\pm 40^\circ$) than needed, while a larger standard deviation or more available data would make the realistic dataset suitable for training the model.

5. Conclusions

A methodology to evaluate power curves through aeroelastic simulations and virtual nacelle lidar measurements is outlined. Specifically, we test multi-dimensional power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions, whose input attributes consist of the mean wind speed, the wind speed variance and the yaw misalignment. The mean wind speed is derived as either hub height wind speed or rotor equivalent wind speed, depending on whether the numerical wind fields are characterized by wind shear.

When properly trained, the multivariate polynomial regressions outperform the IEC standard

power curve. Specifically, when tested on a realistic dataset, which presents wind conditions similar to those of a test site on the west coast of Denmark, the trivariate power curve $P = P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$ predicts the power output with a 48% lower error than the IEC standard power curve. Additionally, the SpinnerLidar measurements increase the accuracy of the multi-dimensional power curve compared to mast-based sonic anemometers, due to a better characterization of the inflow to the rotor.

The optimal value for the degree of the polynomial expressions change depending on the input attributes, the dataset and the measuring device (mast-based anemometry or nacelle-mounted lidar). For the three-dimensional case $P(U, \sigma_u^2, \gamma)$, the minimum error is obtained with a polynomial expression of the 4th order when using both the SpinnerLidar and the sonic measurements. However, a different optimal polynomial degree might be found using a different dataset.

Our results show that multi-dimensional power curves in the form of multivariate polynomial regressions can be a valuable alternative to the IEC standard power curve, with possible improvements in wind turbine power prediction and energy yield assessment.

This work should be extended by testing the same multi-dimensional power curves with either simulations of more realistic flow cases or measurements from a nacelle-mounted SpinnerLidar out in the field. Moreover, it would be interesting to test the same approach under inhomogeneous conditions, i.e. for wind turbines under waked conditions, where the gain in accuracy compared to the IEC standard power curve is expected to be much larger than what found in this work for homogeneous conditions.

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